

Probability of finding habitable planet using transit method

Dhwani Rupali Vani¹, T. Anjali Shivani Reddy¹, Agrita Shrivastava¹, Aashika Patil¹, Hriday Agrawal¹

¹: Society for Space Education Research & Development

Abstract

TESS (NASA's Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite) on June 7 discovered its first Earth-sized planet in its star's habitable zone, where conditions may be just right for liquid water to exist on the surface, called TOI 700 d. I have done the findings of the existence of exoplanets using many detection methods. Although the most successful method, responsible for the discovery of 70% of the exoplanet population, has been the 'Transit Method'. However, there sometimes are several disadvantages in the detection of these foreign planets. For instance, when a glitch is observed in a light curve because of the transmission of data, we can misunderstand it for an exoplanet. In this paper, we have attempted to find the probability of a transit method for detecting the habitable planet.

Methodology

The extent to which an event is likely to occur, measured by the ratio of the favorable cases to the whole number of cases possible.

Summarization of methodology which we used to formulate the approximated probability equation in below flow chart.

Introduction

When we look out for a habitable planet, we start with a word similar to ours. Finding an earth-size planet orbiting around a sun-like star is indeed very difficult. The habitable zone of the star differs from one-to-one system. Hotter stars have wider habitable zones compared to small, dimmer, cooler stars, which have tight habitable zones.

This infographic compares the characteristics of three classes of stars in our galaxy: Sun-like stars are classified as G stars; stars less massive and cooler than our Sun are K dwarfs; and even fainter and cooler stars are the reddish M dwarfs.

Credits: NASA, ESA and Z. Levy (STScI).

Finding the transit of an exoplanet depends on light curve objects, which are data objects which encapsulate the brightness of a star. There is a range of light curves observed based on situation light curve due to single orbiting planet, multiple planets; Eclipsing binaries; Systematic effect because of glitches, multiple observations at same time, because of equipment; Stellar variability.

The dip and width of the light curve depends on the size of the planet, star and also distance between parent star and its planet. If a planet has a small orbital period, the distance between the subsequent transit is also small.

References & Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the guidance of C. Swastik for his guidance throughout this project.

- <https://exoplanets.nasa.gov/search-for-life/habitable-zone/>
- <https://docs.lightkurve.org/index.html>
- <https://lco.global/facebook/exoplanets/transit-method/>

Calculating the DAHz

We attempted to formulate the equation which predicts the habitable exoplanet using the transit method which we named it as 'DAH Equation'. Consider these parameters are independent

The parameters used in equation

F1: Fraction of planets discovered using transit method

F1= 3380/4438 ~ 0.78

F2: Fraction of habitable zone planets discovered by transit method

Till 2014, 1780 exoplanets were discovered out of which 16 are in habitable zones. Number of habitable planets discovered by transit method of detection are:

F2= 5/16 ~ 0.312

F3: Fraction of stars where the star can own a habitable planet.

The stars have to be hotter like the sun with a wider orbiting planet or small, dimmer red dwarf with a tightly orbiting planet.

Considering T is a random variable with probability distribution P_T(L)

Probability of suitable star of age is currently having right temperature.

$$\pi(x) = C_{TO}(x) - \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} C_{TO}(x-L)P_L(L)dl \quad C_{TO}(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x P_{TO}(t)dt$$

If R(t) is suitable star temperature with suitable age.

$$F_3(T) = \int_0^T R(T-x) \pi(x) dx$$

F4: The fraction of stars with one or more planets orbiting around its host star in galaxy

F4 = average number of stars in galaxy having at least one planet orbiting around the host star/ Total number of stars in galaxy

F4 ~ 1

Equation = F1 * F2 * F3 * F4

There are few problems with transit method of detection:

The transit photometry method tends to produce false positives

F5: fraction of false transit while detecting the planets. There are few factors responsible for false positives

F5 = P(Eb) * P(Sv)

Probability of false positives due to eclipsing binary star P(Eb), Roughly 50% of are eclipsing in binary.

P(Eb) ~ 0.5

Stars can vary their luminosity on their own because some stars are pulsating stars or have sun spots or cooler regions on their surface.

P(Sv) = P(Sv_1) + P(Sv_2)

P(Sv_1) is probability of pulsating stars in galaxy = 10,000 / 10^11 = 0.0000001

P(Sv_2) is probability of spots or cooler region = ~ 10^-7

P(Sv) = 10^-7 + 1 = ~ 1

F5 = 1 * 0.5 = 0.5

DAH Equation = F1 * F2 * F3 * F4 * F5 = ~ 0.12122 * F3

Conclusion

Our equation is more like the approximation rather than precision. This attempt of finding Probability of habitable planets using the transit method is made to understand the factors affecting the transit detection method. Our research on DAHz Equation is still going on, we will be updating the latest equation with more parameters. The importance of this equation is to know the current status of our technology and transit methods have detected more than 70% of planets but it doesn't mean it is good enough. We can improve the transit detection method for further space exploration.